

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Set-up and installation documentation

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	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the project (including R4D services)	
	CO	Confidential, only for project and the R4D services	
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Change log

Version ¹	Date	Amended by	Changes
0.1	15-09-2017	Daniele Strigaro	Document creation
0.2	30-09-2017	Daniele Strigaro	Added 4onse-mod documentation
1.0	03-10-2017	Daniele Strigaro	Added 4onse-pcb documentation

Partners involved in the work execution

Versions	Partner Name	People involved
0.1	SUPSI	Daniele Strigaro
0.2	SUPSI	Daniele Strigaro
1.0	SUPSI / UOM	B.H. Sudantha, Dananjaya Bandara, Emeshi Warusavitharana, Daniele Strigaro

NOTES:

For comments / suggestions / contributions to this document, contact the Coordinator of 4onse project at massimiliano.cannata@supsi.ch

For more information on the project 4onse, link to <http://www.4onse.ch>

¹ Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0.

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Executive summary

This document lists the material developed to build the 4onse weather station prototypes. Firstly, the 4onse-mod documentation and secondly the 4onse-pcb set-up material are provided.

1 Documentations

Type	Link	Annex
4onse-mod	link	D01
4onse-pcb	link	D02